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DUNYO TILSHUNOSLIGIDA NUTQIY ETIKETLARNING O'RGANILISHI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Bu maqolada nutqiy etiket birliklarining tasnifi, uni jahon tilshunosligida o'rganilishi, olimlar tomonidan nutqiy etiketga berilgan ta'riflar, nutqiy etiket qoidalari xususida fikr-mulohazalar berilgan. Nutqiy etiketni hodisa sifatida qadimdan o'rganilishi, uning ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan asoslanishi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: nutqiy etiket, ijtimoiy fenomen, ilmiy termin, nutq madaniyati, nutqiy etiket qoidalari, lingvomadaniy.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЕДИНИЦ ЭТИКИ РЕЧИ В МИРОВОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ
АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье даны комментарии по классификации единиц речевого этикета, его изучению в мировой лингвистике, определения, данные речевому этикету учеными, правила речевого этикета. Описаны древние исследования речевого этикета как явления и его научно-теоретическая основа.

Ключевые слова: речевой этикет, социальное явление, научный термин, культура речи, правила речевого этикета, лингвокультурология.

STUDY OF SPEECH ETHICS UNITS IN WORLD LINGUISTICS
ANNOTATION

This article provides comments on the classification of units of speech etiquette, its study in world linguistics, the definitions given to speech etiquette by scholars, the rules of speech etiquette. The ancient study of speech etiquette as an event and its scientific and theoretical basis are described.

Keywords: speech etiquette, social phenomenon, scientific term, speech culture, rules of speech etiquette, linguocultural.

Introduction: Language and its derivative speech are one of the most important means of communication in human society. Speech reflects a person's culture, manners, knowledge, and behavior. This perception is expressed in linguistics through the concept of "speech etiquette". Speech etiquette is a concept that is understood in terms of individual culture and values. In humans, speech etiquette is formed from childhood under the influence of the environment, the situation in the family and society, and other factors. It is natural that speech etiquette varies from nation to nation, depending on the nature of the nation. Various aspects of speech etiquette have been studied not only by linguists, but also by sociologists and culturologists, and a variety of concepts have been put forward (1). Especially in recent years, there has been a growing interest in this issue. Because speech etiquette is becoming one of the most important factors in the interaction between nations and peoples. Although verbal etiquette has existed as a phenomenon for a long time, its scientific study began relatively late, in the mid-20 th century. Oriental, especially Japanese, and Chinese linguistics have focused on this issue since the 1920s, and Western linguistics since the second half of the 20 th century.

Literature Analysis And Methodology: Speech etiquette refers to the special subsystems of a stable national pattern of communication patterns that are accepted by society and need to be used to communicate and maintain it in a targeted way. Russian

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linguist N.I. Formanovskaya describes speech etiquette as follows. "The concept of speech etiquette is a set of rules governing speech behavior, specific national patterns of communication and stable forms of communication adopted by society to establish communication between interlocutors, to maintain and terminate communication for the intended purpose." Conversation produces sentences in a whole pattern in relation to certain patterns of life. They relate to real-life situations and topics of conversation. It is known that all types of such sentences differ from each other, otherwise their types do not differ.

"Speech etiquette" as a scientific term began to be used in Western linguistics in the 60s of the twentieth century and was formed as a separate field. But speech etiquette is a social phenomenon that can be studied and understood through observation. For example, shaking hands in Russia and other European nations causes misunderstanding and disrespect in Japan, while in some Arab countries, kissing by men seems unusual for people of other nationalities. In New Zealand, people are greeted with a nose-to-nose fight, some Oriental people bow, and Tibetans greet each other with their tongues out as an example of the diversity of etiquette. Linguopragmatic study of speech etiquette units expands the ability of two or more peoples to understand each other's culture, mentality, beliefs, traditions, values, to avoid pragmatic mistakes in communication, to increase knowledge about cultural concepts. In the units of Uzbek speech etiquette, speech etiquette has not been studied as a separate science or theory in the works of such thinkers as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farobi, Abu Abdullah al-Khwarizmi, Kaykovus, Yusuf Khas Khojib, Ahmad Yugnaki, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur (2) However, we see that in the works in various fields they have created, a special chapter or chapter has been devoted to this subject. The issue of speech etiquette in Uzbekistan as an object of special research dates back to the end of the twentieth century. Researches of such researchers as E. Begmatov, S. Inomkhodjayevev, Sh. Iskandarova, Y. Tojiev, A. Aripova, N. Mahmudov, R. Rasulov, K. Muydinov, A. Muminova on the issues of Uzbek communication He has made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek culture of speech, as well as the art of speech and the style of oratory.

Discussion And Results:

The first research in this field in world linguistics belongs to Robin Lakoff of California, P. Brown of the United States, S. Levinson and G. Lich of Britain. I. (3). Goffman correct use of reference words and phrases; treat individuals according to their status and level of intimacy in society, and use formal or informal speech correctly and appropriately; emphasizes the correct understanding of language traditions related to specific situations (accepting or rejecting an offer, starting and ending a conversation, etc.) as rules of speech etiquette, and proves its point with examples. According to him, "approved traits and their attitudes towards Facebook are everyone's own prisoner. However, no matter how much people prefer their individual desires, they have to submit to fundamental social constraints"(4).

One of the theorists of speech etiquette, R. Lakoff, describes speech etiquette as "a well-developed pattern of behavior in society" and "a subject that needs to be studied in order to reduce the contradictions in human interaction." In *What the Word Can Do: Speech Etiquette, Pragmatics, and Its Performers*, he suggests the following three principles of speech etiquette: 1) Do not press and keep your distance; 2) Give the interviewee a choice and show respect; 3) Make your audience feel free and friendly. R. Lakoff's principles of speech etiquette are called "Pragmatic Skills" in science, in which it is important to enter into a conversation with the following in mind: Who we are talking to; what we are talking about (topic, field), how we are talking (style). Some of the principles put forward by Lakoff are universal and important not only for Western (European) society, but also for Easterners.

To get the conversation going, P. Grace suggests the following four rules:

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1. The rule of quality (be honest);
2. Quantitative rule (speak briefly);
3. Relationship rule (be appropriate / relevant);
4. Etiquette (be clear)

Although these recommendations were studied in the context of the Rules of Speech Etiquette, P. Grace did not specify whether these rules were based on the principles of his society, or whether they meant universal speech etiquette. J. Thomas, in his article "Mutual Cultural Pragmatic Mistakes," discusses pragmatic misunderstandings in the communication of people who speak different cultures but speak the same language.

Indeed, pragmatic differences in people's ways of thinking, rules of speech, social and national values, lexical connotations, and a number of other factors can lead to errors in communication.

Linguopragmatic study of speech etiquette units expands the ability of two or more peoples to understand each other's culture, mentality, beliefs, traditions, values, avoid mistakes, increase knowledge of pragmatic culture concepts in communication. This, in turn, clarifies the impact of factors such as ethnicity, national language, gender, age, status, ethnicity, economic life, and religion on speech.

Conclusion.

From the above we can draw the following conclusions:

- 1) The term units of speech etiquette is used in various terms in world linguistics;
- 2) It is important to express the units of verbal etiquette sincerely. Active in intimate relationships and inactive in formal relationships;
- 3) In the use of units of verbal etiquette, there are cases when the principles of speech polishing, inaccuracy (abstraction), non-pressure prevail.

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